

RELATIONSHIP OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN CHEMISTRY PRACTICAL IN CHIKUN L.G.A OF KADUNA STATE

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20973919>

ABSTRACT

This study was designed to establish the relationship among four variables, namely: availability/utilization of laboratory resources, school laboratory environment, teachers' and students' attitudes as they might affect chemistry students' academic performance in chemistry practical in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State. A sample of 80 SSIII students drawn from a population of 294 students from 4 schools in the area was used for the study. Three research questions were stated for the study while two instruments (the Assessment of Preparedness for Chemistry Practical Questionnaire & Researcher-Made Practical Chemistry Test) with reliability indices of 0.70 and 0.75 respectively were used to gather data. The data obtained were analyzed by Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and multiple regression analysis. Findings of the study revealed that the independent variables correlated positively with performance ($r = .551-.601$) but failed to correlate among themselves ($p < .001$ at critical $r = .217$). When the variables were taken together, they significantly accounted for a minimal of 18% in explaining the variance in chemistry practical performance ($F:4, 75 = 4.22, p=.004, R^2=.18$). However, the correlations were not statistically significant in predicting the students' performance in practical chemistry. It was recommended, among other things, that availability/utilization of laboratory resources, good school laboratory environment should be marched with their effective utilization to boost chemistry practical performance while at the same time changing the orientation of attitude of teachers and students towards chemistry practical in our senior secondary schools.

Keywords: Relationship, Factors (variables), Performance, Practical Chemistry, SS Students.

Introduction

Chemistry is an important science subject that has greatly contributed to the scientific and technological growth and development of any nation. Its influence permeates virtually all spheres of human life. For instance, we 'taste' chemistry in the food we consume, 'feel' chemistry in the shoes/clothes we wear, 'experience' chemistry in the shelters we live in and in the automobiles that convey us. Little wonder, therefore, why chemistry is made a core subject among the natural sciences and other science-related courses in the Nigerian Education System. Folounrunso and Sunday (2017) noted that, chemistry, by its relevance and functionality in contents, practices and applications, has addressed the needs of the

majority. Its importance as a requirement in undertaking such courses as medicine, pharmacy, nursing and engineering warrants a call by Ogunleye (2014) to teach the subject more effectively. Chemistry is a science that studies the composition, structure, properties of matter as well as the changes that matter undergoes coupled with the attendant energy changes in the processes. This science subject cannot be taught theoretically in abstraction.

Chemistry is an experimental science which should be taught as such to reduce the often perceived difficulty and abstraction commonly reported among students (Sirhan, 2007 & Cruz, 2023). Teaching chemistry experimentally through students-centred hands-on activities

foster the learning of science process and manipulative skills that promote cognition and retention which can engender discoveries and inventions (Cruz, 2023; Ejidike & Oyelana, 2015; Herr and Cunningham, 1999). Besides, learning science by experimentation makes the learning more memorable to the students' senses (Ibrahim et al, 2013) because according to Mohamadi (2018) 75% of what we learn is by the sense of sight, 13% is by hearing, 8% is by touch while 3% each is by smell and taste. This goes to confirm Confucius' 451BC assertion that what we see we remember and what we do we understand. Experimental science such as chemistry requires its teaching and learning in school science laboratories where both the physical and instructional facilities are adequate and the teacher deploys diverse teaching approaches and evaluation methods to take care of the different learners in the course of instructional delivery (Ibe et al 2013; Dan-Ologe & Shittu, 2012; Ejidike & Oyelana 2015). The importance of laboratory instructional facilities/equipment in enhancing understanding and clarifying concepts (Anyadiegwu 2018; Udoh, 2015); promoting active learning and interactive laboratory experience (Enderle & Leeanne, 2016) and stimulating and engaging students to learn at their different levels (Udoh & Etiubon, 2020) cannot be overemphasized. Also, attitude towards anything is very important. It could be favourable, unfavorable or neutral attitude depending on a number of factors. This can impact not only on the teacher's discharge of his duty but also on students' performance. For instance, Thangavel and Selvan (2024) reported of the contribution of favorable attitude to greater academic success among Indian graduate chemistry students.

Chemistry practicals, no doubt, can effectively be carried out in the school science laboratories given that the laboratories are adequately equipped, the teachers have the right attitude and competence to use the facilities for the practicals and the learners (students) are willing to learn under the assumed

prevailing conducive environment of the school laboratories. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council of Nigeria (NECO) in keeping with the goal of our National Policy on Education (Federal Ministry of Education, 2014) that practical work should constitute the main approach for learning chemistry, assign a reasonable percentage score to practical work in the overall assessment of a candidate's performance in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE). According to Osokoya (2018), WAEC allots 25% to a candidate's performance in practical work while NECO apportions 24% for same leaving the theory and objective aspects of the examination with 75% and 72% respectively.

However, students' weaknesses in SSCE such as their inability to draw logical conclusions from what they observed in tests they performed, inability to calculate mass of sample solution, performing tests directly on solid samples instead of using solution of the samples and poor knowledge of simple chemical concepts (WAEC Chief Examiners' Report, 2019), are pointers to what may contribute to the overall students' generally observed poor performance in chemistry (Burton & Twistky 2014; Twistky, 2013; Cho & Poh 2016; Jibrin et al, 2021).

Literature is replete with many factors that affect students' academic performance. With regards to performance in science in the developing countries, De-Silva et al (2018) listed them to include socioeconomic status, parental involvement, school resources, teacher quality and motivation. Other researchers such as Akpan & Gyuse (2016) listed students' study habits. The empirical studies by Babafemi (2019); Olajide et al (2019); Salisu & Samuel (2025); Nwadike (2019); Akor (2019); and Ndirika (2019); all in the Nigerian setting revealed that teacher quality, school resources and student-centered factors are the most influential factors on students' performance in science. A teacher's attitude, is one strong aspect of teacher quality that no doubt can

impact on students` performance. Attitude is disposition towards something and is based on one`s feelings, mode, opinion or belief towards it. Hashi et al (2025) defined attitude as the tendency to acquire a new skill and that, this depends on the characteristics of an individual. Such disposition or acquired skill could be positive or negative, favorable or unfavorable and could be brought to bear on the teaching of chemistry practical. A teacher`s positive and favorable attitude will gender students` better performance and vice versa. Also, students` positive attitude has been shown to significantly affect academic achievement in chemistry (Ndubuisi et al, 2023; Hashi et al ,2025; Malana, 2020). As regards laboratory resources, Hashi et al (2025) reported of a strong positive relationship between utilization of school laboratories and academic performance in chemistry. In the same vein, Issah et al (2023) reported that students` ability to learn meaningfully in science depends thoroughly on availability of laboratory equipment/materials. Ram (2019) is of the same view that availability of chemistry laboratory facilities and their effective utilization for teaching and learning significantly affect students` performance in science. Hashi et al (2025) maintained that the quality of teaching and classroom (laboratory) environment can improve or hinder academic performance.

It is against this background that this study seeks to establish the relationship, if any, among the availability/use of laboratory resources in teaching / learning chemistry practicals, the attitude of the chemistry teachers and that of their students (learners) towards chemistry practical, their various laboratory environment and performance in chemistry.

Statement of the Problem

The prevailing poor performance in science (chemistry) is a thing of concern to all stakeholders in Science Education despite several efforts to stem this trend. This dwindling academic performance apparently extends to practical work in science despite copious empirical evidence by

researchers such as Babafemi (2019), Olajide et al(2019) that teacher quality, school resources and student-centered factors most especially influence students` academic performance in science. Are these factors effectively deployed in school science teaching/learning? This claim needs further investigation. What is much worrisome to the researcher is the WAEC Chief Examiners` Report of Chemistry students` weaknesses in SSCE to the extent that the students cannot draw logical conclusion from laboratory tests they carry out and observe; their adding solid sample instead of solution of the sample to test tubes to heat; additionally, the students` inability to calculate molar mass of solution sample and poor knowledge of simple chemical concepts. This is ridiculous and raises questions as to whether laboratory resources no longer play their role of promoting effective and meaningful learning in our schools. This study is important as it attempts to unravel this puzzle with specific reference to laboratory resources, laboratory environment, students` and teachers` attitude to chemistry practical in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the nature and size of relationship among availability/utilization of laboratory resources, school laboratory environment, chemistry teachers` attitude, students` attitude and academic performance. Specifically, the study was designed to achieve the following objectives:

- i. Establish relationship among availability/utilization of laboratory resources, laboratory environment, teachers` attitude, students` attitude and academic performance of students in chemistry practicals
- ii. Determine the joint contribution of these independent variables to the prediction of students` academic performance in practical chemistry.

iii. Find out the relative contribution of each of the predictor variables to the prediction of students' academic performance in chemistry practicals.

Research Questions

On the basis of the problem and the objectives of the study, the following research questions were formulated:

1. What is the relationship among availability/utilization of laboratory resources, laboratory environment, teachers' attitude, students' attitude and academic performance of students in chemistry practicals?
2. What is the joint contribution of all these independent variables to the prediction of students' performance in chemistry practicals?
3. What is the relative contribution of each of these independent variables to the prediction of students' academic performance in chemistry practicals?

Research Method

The study sought to establish relationship among four independent variables and performance in chemistry practical (PCP). As the predictor variables could not be manipulated having existed before the participants were engaged in the study, the ex post facto research design was used for this study (Kerlinger & Lee(2000). Eighty(80) SSIII chemistry students (in their 3rd term) randomly drawn from four(4) co-educational public senior secondary schools with a total population of 294 students in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State constituted the sample for the study. The use of SSIII students was necessary because the study targeted subjects who were about to write SSCE and the practical chemistry test contents were also based on SSIII school certificate syllabus. Two instruments were used for the study, viz Assessment of Preparedness for Chemistry Practical Questionnaire (APCPQ) and Researcher-Made Practical Chemistry Test (RPCT). The APCPQ had 20 items in all with 5 items each devoted to assessment of availability of resources (ALFE); School Laboratory Environment (SLE);

Chemistry Teachers' Attitude (CTA) towards the conduct of chemistry practical and the Students' Attitude (SA) towards chemistry practical in all the sampled schools.

APCPQ was graded on a 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree(4points), agree (3points), disagree (2points) and strongly disagree (1point). All the items were to be responded to by the chemistry students only. The Researcher-Made Practical Chemistry Test consisted of 25 multiple choice questions lettered A – D. The test questions were set by the researcher on simple volumetric analysis (titrations) and qualitative analysis based on the students' SSIII Syllabus on what they were supposed to have known in readiness for their SSCE that was fast approaching. All the students' preparations for the SSCE were subsumed in their attitude. Each correctly answered question carried 1mark making altogether a total of 25mks for all correctly answered questions. APCPQ and RPCT were face-validated by 4 experts in the field of science education and trial-tested twice with a sample of 50 SSIII chemistry students in Zaria LGA of Kaduna State. The instruments were found valid with reliability indices of 0.70 and 0.75 for APCPQ and RPCT respectively by re-retest approach.

All the instruments were administered to the 80 SSIII students in the sampled schools during normal school session with the aid of their chemistry teachers. They were retrieved and marked and the data collected subjected to analysis using SPSS version 26. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to obtain the intercorrelations among the predictor and predicted variables while standard multiple regression analysis was used to find out the unique and combined contribution of the independent variables to the dependent variable. Standard beta weights were used to assess the importance or other wise of the predictor variables to the prediction of academic performance of the

students in chemistry practicals. The analysis and results are presented in Tables 1 – 3.

Table1: Intercorrelations among predictor and predicted variables

	ALFE	SLE	CTA	SA	PCP
ALFE	1.00	0.111ns	0.053ns	0.122ns	0.601*
SLE		1.00	0.087ns	0.088ns	0.551*
CTA			1.00	0.112ns	0.600*
SA				1.00	0.590*
PCP					1.00

Sig at .05(two tailed);ns= not significant, critical r= 0.217@df=78;p<.001

Table 1 shows the intercorrelation matrix of the study variables. All the predictor variables viz, availability of laboratory facilities, school laboratory environment, chemistry teachers’

attitude and students’ attitude failed to correlate among themselves but correlated positively and significantly with practical chemistry performance: the r value being almost the same.590,.600,.551and.601.

Table2: Regression analysis on performance in chemistry practical with predictor variables entered stepwise

Multiple R=0.429					
R-Squared=0.184					
Adjusted R=0.140					
Standard Error=12.30					
Analysis of variance					
Source of variation	SS	DF	MS	F ratio	P
Regression	2555.331	4	638.833		
Residual	11344.156	75	151.255	4.224	.004
Total	13899.488	79			

***Significant at .05level**

Table 2 is the regression analysis on the practical chemistry performance with the independent variables entered stepwise. It shows the joint contribution of the predictor variables to the prediction of the practical chemistry performance. From the table, the combined effect of the predictor variables gives a multiple

regression coefficient R = 0.429 with R-squared of 0.184. Analysis of variance for the regression yielded F (at df 4, 75) = 4.224, P = .004. The overall regression model is statistically significant. Thus, the independent variables jointly taken accounted for only 18% in explaining the variance in practical chemistry

performance. This represents a minimal effect size.

Table3: Relative importance of the predictor variables to the prediction of performance in chemistry practical

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standard Error
	B Value		
Constant	24.478		5.862
SLE	-4.210		2.914
ALFE	2.046		2.271
CTA	.675		1.164
SA	.596		.659

Not significant at .05level

Table 3 shows the standardized coefficients (beta values) as indices of size of each predictor variable on the predicted variable. The table shows in ascending order, the individual beta values (contributions) of the variables, i.e SA, CTA, ALFE and SLE in predicting practical chemistry performance. All their t-values are statistically not significant implying that there is no single variable dominance in the prediction.

Discussion of Findings

The aim of the study was to determine the nature and size of relationship among availability/utilization of laboratory resources, school laboratory environment, chemistry teachers’ attitude, students’ attitude and academic performance and how these independent variables individually and jointly contribute to the prediction of academic performance in chemistry practical among senior secondary students in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State. The predictor variables correlated positively and

significantly with performance in practical chemistry test with their r-values being almost equal (nearly .6). This finding aligns with those Ndubuisi & Okoli (2023), Hashi et al (2025), Issah et al (2023) and Ram (2019).

This shows that the performance in chemistry practical was partly influenced by these variables. However, the predictor variables did not correlate with each other implying there is no multicollinearity; each predictor variable having a minimal contribution that cannot be reliably detected at $N=80$. Regression analysis on performance in chemistry practical with the predictor variables entered stepwise reveals that the joint contribution of the independent variables in explaining the variance in chemistry practical performance is about 18% ($F(4, 75) = 4.224, p < .05$).

However, when the beta – values of the independent variables were examined as indices of relative contributions of the variables to the prediction of performance in practical chemistry, the beta values for school laboratory environment ranked highest (-.630 regardless of the negative sign) while the students’ attitude came the least (.275). But their contributions to the prediction from the t-values were not statistically significant ($p > .05$), an indication of no single dominant variable in the prediction. The minimal contribution of the predictor variables to academic performance may be partly explained by the fact that laboratory resources were not properly utilized in the sampled schools.

This shows that no matter how excellent the school laboratory environment may be (the physical facilities, teaching and evaluation

methods, available laboratory resources), if they are not properly and adequately utilized, they amount to nothing in affecting students' learning and performance in chemistry practical. This finding lends credence to Udoh and Etiubon's (2018) discovery that biology and chemistry teachers in secondary schools rarely utilize the few available laboratory facilities in the teaching – learning process. This exposes the teachers' attitude of indifference in part or a question of their incompetence in the use of laboratory resources and /or effective teaching evaluation method. The students' attitude should also not be overlooked. Though their attitude, like that of their teachers, was positively correlated to performance but the contribution of attitude was not significant in predicting their performance. This is contrary to the findings of Thangavel and Selvan (2024), Xu and Lewis(2011), Dalgety et al (2006), who recorded between strong to moderate significant contributions to performance in a chemistry course. In this study, the teachers' and students' attitude must have been unfavorable to the chemistry practical course.

Conclusion

This study shows that there exists a positive relationship among availability/utilization of laboratory resources, laboratory environment, teachers' attitude and students' attitude and performance in chemistry practical but the relationship was

References

- Akpan, J, O & Gyuse, E, Y. (2016). Effects of Study habit mediation package (SHMP) on senior secondary chemistry students' achievement and retention of electrolysis concepts. *International Journal of Education, Science, humanities, mathematics, and environmental studies* 8(1&2), 49-59.
- Akor, V.(2019). Teacher quality effects on senior secondary school students: implication for the agricultural

not statistically significant in predicting performance. It argues that availability of laboratory resources and good school laboratory environment without adequate and their proper utilization cannot contribute to positive effect on students' academic performance. Similarly, unfavorable attitude of both the teachers of chemistry and their students will undoubtedly contribute negatively the overall students' performance not only in chemistry practical but also in the entire subject.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There should be adequate, proper and timely utilization of chemistry laboratory resources and good school laboratory environment by chemistry teachers in the teaching /learning of chemistry practicals. Such resources should also be provided by the school authorities on time and not at the 11th hour to SSCE.
2. The teachers' and students' attitude towards chemistry practicals needs a good and favourable re-orientation. The Head of Science can periodically do this by organizing small workshops both for teachers and students.
3. Above all, our school laboratories should be adequately furnished with facilities/equipment/materials and the environment well enriched.

science teachers in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Contemporary Studies* 3(1), 1-10.

- Anyaiegwu, C. O. (2018). Availability and Utilization of Laboratory Resources in Teaching and Learning Biology in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. Published Project Submitted to the Department of Science Education, Godfrey Okoye University.
- Babalemi, A. J. (2019). Impacts of prior explosive to lab apparatus on acquisition of process skills, achievement & retention among sec students, Giwa

- Zone, Nigeria Kubanni Repository, Ahmadu Bell University.
- Burton, D & Twisky, E. (2014). The Relative Effectiveness of Rehearsal and Team-assisted Instructional Strategies on Students' Learning Outcomes in Selected Difficult Chemistry Concepts. *Journal of Evaluation and Instruction*, Vol 19 (1), 95-103.
- Cho, L. & Poh, Y.T (2016). Effects of Rehearsal Learning Strategy on Chemistry Achievement of high School Students in Singapore. *International Journal of Education, Science, Humanities, Mathematics and Environmental Students*, 8 (1&2), 1-10.
- Cruz, J. D. L. (2023). Why chemistry is so hard. www.learntblog@2024.
- Dalgety, J., Coll, R. K. & Jones, A. (2006). Development of Chemistry Attitude and Experiences Questionnaires. *Journal for Research in Science Teaching*, 40(7) 649 – 668. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.10103>.
- Dan-Ologe, I. A & Shittu, A.O.(2012). Improving the Standard of teaching and Learning of Practicals in our Secondary Schools: Emphasis on Biology and Chemistry Practicals. *Journal of Qualitative Education*, 8 (1), 1 – 5.
- De-Silva A, Khatibi A & Azam, S. M. F. (2018). What Factors affect Secondary School Students performance in Science in the developing countries? A conceptual model for Exploration. *European Journal of Education studies* 4(6). <https://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejes.vol.0.1613>
- Ejidike. P. & Oyelana, A. A(2015). Factors Influencing Effective Teaching of Chemistry: A Case Study of Some Selected High Schools in Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality, Eastern Cape Province, South Africa. *International Journal Education Sciences*, 8(3), 605-617.
- Enderle, P. J & Learnne, R. B.(2016). Students' Laboratory Manual for Argument –driven Inquiry in Chemistry. <http://chronicle.com/article/thefight-for-classroom/19431>.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2014). National Policy on Education. Abuja. NERDC press.
- Folounrunso, B. E. & Sunday, A. O. (2017). Relative Effectiveness of Guided Discovery and Demonstration Teaching Techniques on Students' Performance in Chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools in Ile-Ife, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 2(9), 664-678
- Hashi, A. O., Mohamud, A. O & Farah, A. M. (2025). Factors influencing undergraduate chemistry performance: A study on attitude, laboratory use, and teaching methods at Somali National University. *International Journal of Education, culture & society* 10(1) <https://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com>. Doi 10.11648/j.ij.20251000.11
- N. & Cunningham, J. (1999). Hands-on Chemistry Activities with Real Life Applications-Contents. John Willey Jossey-Bass Publishers, www.csun.edu.
- Ibe, J. O., Adah, S. A & Ihejiamaizu, C. C.(2013). Assessment of Secondary School Chemistry Teachers' Quality through Identification and Use of Laboratory Apparatus in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(5), 135 -141.
- Ibrahim, N. H. Surif, J., Hui, K. P. & Yaakub, S.(2013). Typical Teaching Method Applied in Chemistry Experiment. *Procedia-social & Behavioral Sciences*, (116), 4946 – 4954.
- Issah, I., Baalongbuoro, V. & Afram, O. S. (2023). The impact of laboratory practical activities on students' academic performance at Queen of peace senior high School in the Nadowil-Kaleo district of the upper west region of Ghana. *International Journal scientific Research and Management*, 11(3), 2727-2739. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/V11i03.elz>
- Jibrin A. G., Abba, H. I & Mohammed, I. (2021). Effects of Cooperative Learning Strategy on the Academic Performance of Biology Students in Senior Secondary School in Azare Metropolis. *International Journal of Research and Policy Making* 4(1), 683 – 691.
- Kerlinger, F. N. & Lee, H. B.(2000). Foundations of Behavioural Research (4th Ed). Harcourt College Publishers.
- Ndirika, M. C. (2019). Achievement variation of Basic science student taught teacher-centered teacher/student-centered instructions in Kaduna state, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational & Social Research*
- Ndubusi, C. B. & Okoli J. A.(2023). Academic self-concept & Attitude towards chemistry as predictors of Senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Anambra State. *IJRES* 3(5) 20-36. *International of Research in Education and Sustainable Development* <https://www.ijaar.org>.
- Nwadike, I. S. (2019) Teacher quality as predictor of student learning satisfaction in secondary school in Rivers State. *Babcock University Journals* 126-143
- Malana, M. (2020). Attitude & level of performance of chemistry students. *International Journal of Psychosocial rehabilitation* 24(7), 10148-10154. Doi:10.37200/IJPR/V/2417/PR271028

- Mohamdi, F.(2018). Learning is what they remember after they have forgotten all that you said. www.Linkedin.com/impulde/learning.
- Ogunleye, B. O. (2014). Prerequisite Knowledge and Attitudes to Chemistry Practical as Correlates of Students' Performance and Practical Skills in Senior School Chemistry Niger Delta *Journal of Education*, 6(1&2), 80-88.
- Olajide, S. O, Adebisi, T. A. & Tewogbade, T. A. (2019). Assessment of Laboratory resources, teachers and students' involvement in practical activities in basic science in Junior secondary Schools in Osun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational & social Research*.<https://www.semanticscholar.org>.
Doi:10.1515JESR-2017-001.
- Osokoya, M. M. & Nwazota, C (2018). Problem Based and School-types Contributory Factors to the Senior Secondary School Students' Practical Skills in Chemistry. *Journal of the International Society for Teacher Education* 22(1), 7-18.
- Ram, B. P. (2019), An assessment of availability and utilization of laboratory facilities for teaching science at secondary Level. *International council of Association Science Educators*, 30(1), 75-81 <https://doi.org/10.33828/sei.V030i1.9>
- Salisu, A. D. & Samuel I. R. (2025). Effect of laboratory approach on interest and achievement of students in energy concepts in Keffi, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of modeling of applied science research*. Doi:10.70382-caijmasr. v7i9002
- Sirhan, G(2007).Leaning Difficulties in Chemistry: An overview. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 4(2), 2-20.
- Thangavel, K. & Selvan, A(2024), The Relationship between Attitude towards Chemistry and Academic Performance in Undergraduate Chemistry Course. www.eduspectra.com,6(1), 83-88.
- Twisky, F. I. (2013). Effect of Rehearsal Learning Strategy on the Achievement and Self-concept in School Chemistry. *Journal of Science Education*, 5(1), 19-24
- Udo, N. M & Etiubon, R. U. (2020). Availability and Utilization of Laboratory Facilities for Teaching Carbohydrates in Senior Secondary Schools in Uyo Education Zone, Akwa Ibom State. *International Journal of Education and Research* 8(5), 1-14.
- Udo, N. M. (2015). Effects of Computer Simulation and Charts on Biology Students' Academic Performance and Retention on the Concepts of Nervous Coordination. Unpublished Dissertation, Department of Science Education, University of Uyo, Uyo.
- West African Examination Council (2019), May/Jure Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations: Chief Examiners' Reports. WAEC, Secretariat.
- Xu, X. & Lewis, J. E(2011). Refinement of Chemistry Attitude Measure for College Students *Journal of Chemical Education*,88(5),561-568.<https://doi.org/10.1021/ed900071q>